

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STATE SYSTEM PROCUREMENT

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Abstract: The thesis examines the basics of organizing the public procurement system, strategies for optimizing the system, including strengthening control and monitoring, introducing effective liability measures, as well as the role of modern information technologies in increasing the transparency and openness of the public procurement process.

Key words: public procurement, prospects for optimization of public procurement, monitoring, budget funds, government customers, participants, suppliers.

The current trend in the development of the financial sector at the global level is characterized by the need to further ensure the effective, targeted and rational use of the state's financial resources. In this context, the first place comes to the sphere of procurement by the state, in order to meet the needs in the course of performing its functions and tasks. Accordingly, effective regulation of the public procurement process is a priority for all countries.

In the modern world, the public procurement system plays a key role in meeting the needs of the state and society for various goods and services. The public procurement is the acquisition by the state of goods (works, services) at the expense of public funds, in order to meet the needs of government customers. ^[1]

The process of meeting the needs of the state, territories and regions, expressed in state needs, is determined in accordance with the legislation of a given country.

The basis for meeting state needs is the state order for the supply (purchase) of goods, works and services.

A state order is an application from the state to purchase certain products to cover certain needs of society, which is a specific list of goods, works and services purchased by a specific government body.

Public procurement is a form of government spending. Before talking about government procurement, it is necessary to understand what government spending is.

Government expenditures are funds allocated to financially support the tasks and functions of the state and local government.

The concept is considered within the framework public administration and fiscal policy.

Public procurement is a predominant part of government spending and is important in the socio-economic development of the country. Taking part in government regulation and stimulation of economic processes in the country, through government orders from the state, demand for goods and services is formed.

The system faces a number of situations that require attention and solutions for its continued effectiveness.

Over the past years, experts and public figures have drawn attention to a number of factors that can influence the procurement process, transparency and efficiency in the use of public funds.

One of the most acute problems faced by participants in the public procurement market is discrepancies in the actual delivery times of goods and services to the stated requirements. In general, the delivery time for goods should not exceed 7 days, but recently there are increasingly cases where this period is significantly exceeded.

The main reasons for this situation may be various factors, including reduced competition in the market and lobbying for the interests of certain enterprises. Which leads to mistrust on the part of entrepreneurs and a lack of faith in the possibility of winning in fair trades.

To solve this problem, a number of measures are proposed to improve the situation. In particular, you can borrow from the experience of other countries where the minimum delivery time for goods is a more suitable period of time.

In addition, it is important to optimize the contract monitoring and control system to ensure more effective suppression of violations and improve confidence in the public procurement system as a whole.

The next important task affecting the efficiency of the public procurement system is the lack of supervisory control over the compliance of the delivered goods or services with the stated requirements. As a result, a situation often occurs when the customer receives a product or service that does not meet the declared characteristics or quality. In addition, insufficient control over the conformity of the goods or services being delivered creates conditions for the use of low-quality goods and services in government organizations, which ultimately affects the quality of the services provided and increases the costs of providing them.

To solve this, it is necessary to strengthen the mechanisms of responsibility for violation of public procurement rules for all subjects of public procurement. In addition, to improve control over the compliance of the delivered goods or services with the stated requirements, an audit and monitoring system should be introduced using modern information technologies. Automating the process of monitoring and analyzing data will help improve the efficiency and efficiency of checking the quality of goods and services.

Finally, it is important to ensure transparency and openness in the process of monitoring the quality of goods and services supplied under public procurement. Publication of the results of inspections and audits, the availability of information on the implementation of contracts will help increase confidence in the public procurement system and ensure effective control over the quality of goods and services provided.

Thus, the solution to insufficient control over the conformity of the delivered goods or services requires an integrated approach and the introduction of a number

of measures aimed at strengthening monitoring and control over the quality of goods and services supplied under public procurement.

In conclusion, the areas discussed above in the public procurement system require prompt attention and comprehensive solutions. Insufficient delivery times, insufficient collateral, and lack of sufficient supervisory control can affect the efficiency of the public procurement system.

To solve these problems, it is necessary to take a set of measures, including strengthening control and monitoring by government agencies, developing an effective system of fines and liability for violations, as well as introducing modern information technologies to improve the transparency and openness of the public procurement process.

However, it is also important to consider that successfully solving these problems requires the cooperation and interaction of all stakeholders, including government agencies, entrepreneurs, public organizations and civil society. Only in this case can the effective functioning of the public procurement system be ensured, contributing to the sustainable development of the economy and ensuring the interests of all market participants.

Therefore, drastic measures need to be taken to improve the public procurement system to ensure transparency, competitiveness and efficiency of this important segment of the country's economy.

List of used literature

1. Finance. Module 5: Public procurement: Textbook for undergraduate studies / R.G. Tashmatova; – T.: “TAHRIRIY NASHRIYOT”, 2023. – 272 p.
2. Mamedova N.A. Management of state and municipal procurement: textbook. –M.: Publishing House-Yurait, 2022. – 421 p.
3. Malikov T, Kobulov K. Models of market economy formation and Interaction of fiscal policy. International Journal of Economic Growth and Environmental Issues-ISSN.:2321-6247.

4. TS Malikov, OO Olimjonov. The merits of the ancestors in the formation and development of financial and tax science. 2021
5. Malikov TS, Jalilov PT. Budget tax policy. Tashkent. Academy. 2011.
6. Malikov T, Haydarov N. State budget. Textbook/Tashkent Financial Institute. T.:“Economics and Finance. 2007:84.

